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THE USE OF CONNECTORS AS A TOOL FOR CONTROLLING TURNOVER COSTS¹

A UTILIZAÇÃO DE CONECTORES COMO FERRAMENTA DE CONTROLE DE CUSTOS DE ROTATIVIDADE

Rafaela Amâncio Armacollo²

Eloisa Aparecida Cecília dos Santos³

Valter da Silva Faia⁴

Bruna Mantovanni de Mattos⁵

ABSTRACT

This article aimed to analyze whether individuals identified as "connectors" possess a combination of innate characteristics and abilities that make them personally engaged, prone to relating to others, and capable of influencing the relationships of other group members. The study investigated the role of these "connectors" in the context of a given individual or group within an organization. Furthermore, the effects of connectors on the relationships and interactions among group members were examined. Data collection was conducted through an online questionnaire. The data were analyzed using confirmatory factor analysis and subsequently multiple linear regression to identify patterns of relationship and influence within the group. The results of this research provided insights into the role of "connectors" in group dynamics and their influence on collective outcomes within an organization. This research shows that employees who identify as connectors, or who can recognize other colleagues with this characteristic, have a positive relationship with their level of job satisfaction.

Keywords: management control, cost control, strategic cost management, turnover costs.

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² Universidade Estadual de Maringá. pg404402@uem.br

³ Universidade Estadual de Maringá. eloisa.cecilio.santos@gmail.com

⁴ Universidade Estadual de Maringá. vsfaia@uem.br

⁵ Universidade Estadual de Maringá. pg403244@uem.br

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RESUMO

Este artigo teve como objetivo analisar se os indivíduos identificados como "conectores" possuem uma combinação de características e habilidades inatas que os tornam pessoalmente envolvidos, propensos a se relacionar com os outros e capazes de influenciar os relacionamentos dos demais membros do grupo. O estudo investigou o papel desses "conectores" no contexto de um determinado indivíduo ou grupo dentro de uma organização. Além disso, foram examinados os efeitos dos conectores nos relacionamentos e interações entre os membros do grupo. A coleta de dados ocorreu por meio de questionário online. Os dados foram analisados por meio de análise fatorial confirmatória e na sequência por regressão linear múltipla, para identificar padrões de relacionamento e influência dentro do grupo. Os resultados desta pesquisa forneceram insights sobre o papel dos "conectores" na dinâmica dos grupos e sua influência nos resultados coletivos dentro de uma organização. Pode-se observar nesta pesquisa, que funcionários que se identificam como conectores ou que conseguem reconhecer outros colegas de trabalho com essa característica, possuem uma relação positiva com o grau de satisfação dentro do ambiente de trabalho.

Palavras-chave: controle gerencial, controle de custos, gestão estratégica de custos, custos de rotatividade.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations make considerable efforts to manage employee turnover and to prevent the associated costs from becoming excessive (AUTREY, BAUER, JACKSON & KLEVSKY, 2019; DESS & SHAW, 2001; SHAW, GUPTA, & DELERY, 2005). Examples of these costs include the identification, selection, and training of new employees, as well as the loss of experienced or productive workers (AUTREY et al., 2019; DESS & SHAW, 2001; SHAW, GUPTA, & DELERY, 2005).

In this context, the management control system becomes a highly valuable mechanism that can be implemented either directly or indirectly (RADTKE, SPEKLE & WIDENER, 2022). According to studies in the field of management accounting (AUTREY et al., 2019), indirect control proves to be more effective, as it demonstrates greater trust in the individual within the

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organization. Direct controls are those carried out explicitly, whereas indirect controls are more subtle (RADTKE et al., 2022).

An example of indirect control is clan control, in which individuals' behaviors are encouraged or discouraged through group approval. Because it is implemented in a more discreet manner, employees tend to be more inclined to act accordingly, as they do not feel directly coerced or obligated, but rather perceive that they are acting of their own free will (RADTKE et al., 2022).

Thus, based on the study conducted by Autrey et al. (2019), there is a form of indirect management control exercised within groups by individuals known as "connectors." According to the study, having a connector in a work group significantly reduces undesirable turnover rates (AUTREY et al., 2019).

According to the same study, connectors are those who create a more pleasant work environment through social interaction (AUTREY et al., 2019). This means that individuals within a work group who act as "connectors" reduce the intention to leave the workplace among those who previously felt excluded or not integrated into the organizational environment (AUTREY et al., 2019).

Maintaining a cohesive work group is beneficial for organizations, as there are costs associated with hiring, training, and employee dismissal (RADTKE et al., 2022). Therefore, increasing the level of involvement and commitment of managers and employees is part of strategic management, as it serves as a tool for cost reduction (ROCHA, 1999).

This leads to the research question: "Can the presence of at least one connector in the workplace contribute to reducing turnover costs within an organization?" To answer this question, a quantitative descriptive study was conducted, in which a group of individuals working in various fields responded to a structured questionnaire regarding the identification of "connectors" within an organizational environment.

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Analyzing this scenario and considering the lack of studies in Brazil addressing the topic of “connectors,” two research gaps emerge. The first is to determine whether the presence of at least one connector in an organization positively influences the reduction of employees’ turnover intentions. The second is to verify whether connectors within organizations can be considered a tool for reducing turnover costs. The results of this study revealed that having a connector in the workplace reduces employees’ turnover intentions and is positively related to job satisfaction and group identification, which contributes to lowering turnover costs and provides the company with a competitive advantage in the market.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Connectors as a management control tool

Initially, connectors are defined as individuals with natural characteristics and skills for relating to others and/or capable of influencing the relationships of others (AUTREY et al., 2019). In summary, connectors can be described as individuals who are able to foster a positive culture of social cohesion, along with open communication and fair treatment within groups.

Connectors are able to build links or establish relationships among people because, when inserted into groups, they can facilitate a more positive group experience (or culture), strengthening connections among members by promoting equality and inclusion (AUTREY et al., 2019; PENTLAND, 2010). Employee motivation, together with the sharing of relevant knowledge among individuals within an organization, can create a more effective and efficient way of working within the organizational environment (AUTREY et al., 2019; MILGROM & ROBERTS, 1992; JENSEN & MECKLING, 1995).

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In this sense, connectors may be individuals with prosocial characteristics - that is, people who genuinely enjoy cultivating relationships for personal or altruistic reasons (AUTREY et al., 2019; PENNER, DOVIDIO, PILIAVIN, & SCHROEDER, 2005; KELTNER, KOGAN, PIFF, & SATURN, 2014). Thus, individuals identified as prosocial have been described as good team players, possessing agreeable personalities (i.e., warm, friendly, and able to relate well to others) and showing empathy toward other people (AUTREY et al., 2019; PENNER et al., 2005; KELTNER et al., 2014).

Maximizing employee retention within the organization and the returns on their training involves both economic and strategic management, since economic management focuses on financial results, while strategic management is broader, as it aims to keep the company operating and maintaining a competitive advantage in the market (ROCHA, 1999).

Organizations make significant efforts to manage voluntary employee turnover in order to avoid excessive turnover-related costs, because the higher the turnover, the greater the costs associated with replacement, identification, training, and the loss of experienced or productive employees (AUTREY et al., 2019; DESS & SHAW, 2001; SHAW, GUPTA & DELERY, 2005). When members of an organization share a common perspective through their actions and intentions, this is referred to as strategy. Moreover, strategy can be understood as a pattern or model of behavior (MINTZBERG, 1988; ROCHA, 1999). To create these shared perspectives and behavioral patterns, connectors are necessary.

Autrey et al. (2019) argue that connectors can be effective within organizations that seek to reduce the risk of excessive voluntary turnover. This influence over different employees can be achieved through mechanisms within the management control system (MCS) that shape work groups.

A certain level of voluntary turnover is expected - and sometimes even desired - by organizations, as it may foster innovation or help avoid stagnation.

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However, excessive turnover should be avoided so that its associated costs do not become too high (AUTREY et al., 2019; DESS & SHAW, 2001; SHAW et al., 2005). This is because turnover costs include the loss of specialized human capital, as well as the costs of replacing and training new or reassigned personnel. It is important to note that control mechanisms aimed at reducing turnover - such as selection, placement, promotion, and reward systems - can be costly and may have varying levels of effectiveness (AUTREY et al., 2019; MCEVOY & CASCIO, 1987; PARKER, 2014; SHERIDAN, 1992).

Connectors as a tool for controlling turnover costs

Turnover costs include turnover intention, which is defined as an employee's voluntary decision to request termination from the company (GELENCSÉR et al., 2023). Previous studies have addressed this topic (LUZ & BOENTE, 2024; SANTOS & SANTOS, 2022); however, they did not consider the presence of connector employees.

With the aim of avoiding these turnover costs, and based on the arguments presented (AUTREY et al., 2019; MCEVOY & CASCIO, 1987; PARKER, 2014; SHERIDAN, 1992; DESS & SHAW, 2001; SHAW et al., 2005; MINTZBERG, 1988; ROCHA, 1999; SHAW, GUPTA & DELERY, 2005), it is argued that the implementation of connectors in the workplace can be considered a cost-control tool, as it may reduce undesirable employee turnover.

However, it is important to consider the incentives that organizations may offer to connectors and their own turnover intentions, since retaining connectors within the organization can be challenging due to one of their key characteristics (AUTREY et al., 2019). Because of their tendency to build new connections, they may encounter more attractive job opportunities, and they may also feel burdened by the responsibility of maintaining harmony within the work group (AUTREY et

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al., 2019). This is because not all individuals respond in the same way to such stimuli, and some group members may be reluctant or difficult to manage.

On the other hand, human capital is the resource that keeps organizations alive, as no company exists without people, and one of the most prominent concepts in human capital management is when the organization adopts a team-oriented structure (RADTKE et al., 2022). In this sense, an important point to consider is that when employees do not have “connectors” with whom they can share information, this can lead to a lack of trust in their colleagues and managers, since connectors act as facilitators of communication between team members and management (AUTREY et al., 2019).

This aspect can significantly influence the decision to change jobs, as trust plays a crucial role in establishing behavioral norms among individuals within organizations (LAU et al., 2008). Trust in managers is particularly important, as it can enhance subordinates’ cooperation, willingness to reciprocate, improve information sharing, and reduce opportunistic behavior (JONES, 1995; MAYER & DAVIS, 1999; FISHER et al., 2005).

Previous empirical studies on the effects of trust behavior generally support these claims. For example, research by Van Rinsum and Verbeeten (2012) showed that higher levels of trust in managers are associated with greater motivation to exert effort, which can lead to improved individual performance, as demonstrated in other studies (GIBBS et al., 2004). Sholihin and Pike (2009) found that higher levels of trust in managers are linked to stronger organizational commitment and, consequently, greater identification with the organization.

In contrast, when employees experience distrust, the work environment becomes characterized by a lack of transparency, leading to high levels of anxiety, stress, and frustration (LAU & BUCKLAND, 2001), which discourages a sense of individual belonging to the organization. Finally, Costigan et al. (2011) showed that trust can reduce turnover intention. Conversely, when individuals do

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not trust their managers, they may believe that their performance is undervalued or perceive evaluation outcomes as unfair, which can result in lower effort and a higher likelihood of withdrawal (PRENDERGAST & TOPEL, 1993).

Organizational identification influences individuals' behavior regarding group participation. As noted by Ellemers et al. (1999, p. 372), those who strongly identify with their organization demonstrate greater commitment, involvement, and investment in the group (i.e., the organization). Individuals who feel a sense of belonging to the organization tend to hold more positive beliefs about it, collaborate more with colleagues, and exhibit superior performance (ASHFORTH & MAEL, 1989; VAN DICK et al., 2006; WALUMBWA et al., 2008).

Thus, it is argued that implementing connectors in the workplace can serve as a cost-control tool, as it helps prevent expenses related to the loss of investments in hiring, training, and retaining employees. To test the plausibility of this argument, three hypotheses were developed and statistically examined:

H1: Compared to groups without a connector, groups that include a connector will have lower turnover intentions.

H2: Groups with at least one connector and a high level of satisfaction will have lower turnover intentions than groups with at least one connector and a low level of satisfaction.

H3: Groups with at least one connector and a high level of identification with the company will have lower turnover intentions than groups with at least one connector and a low level of identification with the company.

METHODOLOGY

This study consists of a quantitative descriptive research, conducted through data collection (survey) using a structured online questionnaire (Appendix 1), answered by employees from private companies across a wide range of fields (SAMPIERI, COLLADO & LUCIO, 2013; WALLIMAN, 2015;

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MATIAS-PEREIRA, 2016). These include administrative, commercial, accounting, education, finance, photography, graphic design, music, legal, information technology, and statistical analysis sectors.

Thus, the questionnaire is composed of items extracted from scientific articles, and these items have been previously applied and validated in prior studies (AUTREY et al., 2019; HAESEBROUCK, VAN DEN ABEELE & WILLIAMSON, 2021; ALVES & LOURENÇO, 2021). For the purposes of this study, the questionnaire was administered to individuals who are currently active in their professional roles, that is, individuals working in private companies. This target group was selected because the study focuses on analyzing the topic from a managerial and strategic perspective, and these individuals are involved in organizations that require the use of such accounting tools (AUTREY et al., 2019; ROCHA, 1999; RADTKE et al., 2022). Over the course of one week, data were collected from 82 participants, all of whom responded voluntarily, and all responses were considered valid.

A 5-point Likert scale was used in the questionnaire, where strongly disagree = 1, partially disagree = 2, neither agree nor disagree = 3, partially agree = 4, and strongly agree = 5. The questionnaire consisted of 32 structured questions measured using the Likert scale, along with seven semi-structured questions aimed at characterizing the respondents. This method is widely used to obtain a range of responses to a specific question, and its popularity since its creation is due to its ease of understanding and application, as well as its adaptability to different research needs (EDMONSON, 2005; HODGE & GILLESPIE, 2003).

Initially, the questionnaire began with structured questions, the first of which addressed the respondents' level of interaction with their coworkers. Subsequently, respondents were asked about their coworkers' level of interaction toward them. Next, respondents were asked about their level of satisfaction within

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the company. This was followed by questions regarding their professional outlook within the company, corresponding to turnover intentions. The structured section concluded with questions about the respondents' identification with their group and work environment (AUTREY et al., 2019; HAESEBROUCK, VAN DEN ABEELE & WILLIAMSON, 2021; ALVES & LOURENÇO, 2021).

To characterize the respondents, the questionnaire included questions about: the number of years they have worked at the company, the number of people they work with directly, their sector/area of activity, gender, age, and level of education. The collected data were tabulated using Excel spreadsheets, and statistical tests were conducted using the Jamovi software (THE JAMOVI PROJECT, 2022).

Factor analyses were conducted, focusing on the variables under study. Convergent and discriminant validity tests were also performed. For convergent validity, the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) must present a value greater than 0.5 to avoid issues, indicating that the variable strongly represents the construct under study, meaning each variable is sufficiently reliable on its own (BECKER, 2015; GALLUCCI & JENTSCHKE, 2021; R CORE TEAM, 2021; ROSSEEL, 2019; REVELLE, 2019).

However, for discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE must be greater than the values of the variables in the correlation matrix. In this case, variables may interact with variables from other constructs in the model. This indicates that the variables complement each other, as the constructs are interconnected, meaning one variable may influence another (BECKER, 2015; GALLUCCI & JENTSCHKE, 2021; R CORE TEAM, 2021; ROSSEEL, 2019; REVELLE, 2019).

The five variables were defined as follows: (1) Self-Interactivity (IP); (2) Coworker Interactivity (IC); (3) Level of Satisfaction (STF); (4) Professional Outlook (PP); and (5) Group Identification (IG) and were organized into five

separate blocks in the questionnaire. The Self-Interactivity (IP) variable refers to statements aimed at assessing whether the employee considers themselves a connector; Coworker Interactivity (IC) refers to statements intended to verify whether the respondent works with a connector; Level of Satisfaction (STF) examines whether the employee feels satisfied within their work group.

Professional Outlook (PP) refers to statements that assess whether the employee intends to leave the company within a relatively short period (up to one year), thus analyzing turnover intentions. The Group Identification (IG) variable aims to determine whether the employee feels welcome and well-integrated into the work environment. Control variables were also analyzed subsequently.

The results of the various factor analyses indicate that the tested variables are reliable. In addition, convergent validity of the scales was confirmed, indicating whether the items defining each construct strongly load onto it, and discriminant validity was also assessed, examining whether items have strong correlations with other factors (FAIA, 2014). These results can be observed in Table 1.

Table 1 – Correlation Matrix

	IP		IC		STF		PP		IG
IP	—								
IC	0.324	**	—						
STF	0.325	**	0.45	***	—				
IG	0.308	**	0.38	***	0.726	***	—		
PERS	-0.11		0.18		-0.36	***	-0.32	**	—
Média	2.65		3.22		3.52		2.74		3.28
DP	1.02		1.05		0.998		1.41		1.13
Alpha	0.87		0.93		0.843		0.858		-
AVE	0.558		0.63		0.73		0.619		0.49
RAIZ AVE	0.747		0.79		0.854		0.787		0.7

Note: * p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

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It can be seen that the correlation matrix includes all independent and dependent variables. Factor loadings were analyzed, and those with low strength were removed, which improved the AVE values. According to Table 1, the AVE values indicate that IP explains 55.8% of the model; IC explains 63.1%; STF explains 73%; PP explains 61.9%; and although IG presents 49.1%, it was decided to retain it in the model. Since the acceptable threshold is at least 0.5, the average values were satisfactory for nearly all variables. Therefore, the results are presented below.

RESULTS

As previously stated, this study had the following objectives: (1) to verify whether the existence of at least one connector in an organization positively influences the reduction of employees' turnover intentions; and (2) to determine whether connectors within organizational environments can be considered a tool for reducing turnover costs. Three hypotheses were developed to address the research question: "Can the presence of at least one connector in the workplace contribute to reducing turnover costs within an organization?" Thus, all hypotheses were tested, validated, and supported either fully or partially. However, before analyzing the results of the hypotheses, the tests conducted are described. Table 2 presents the characterization of the sample.

Regarding the categorization carried out to map the characteristics of the participants in this study, 51% (n = 42) of the respondents were female, 48% (n = 39) were male, and 1% (n = 1) preferred not to disclose their gender. The average age of participants was approximately 34 years (33.8), with a standard deviation of approximately 11 years (10.9). As for the educational level of the respondents, the majority - 37% (n = 30) - held a specialization degree, followed by master's degree holders and individuals with undergraduate degrees, each representing 24% (n = 20) of the sample. Doctoral degrees accounted for 10% (n = 8), while only 5% (n = 4) had completed secondary education.

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Table 2 – Characterization of the sample (n=82)

Regarding the respondent		Regarding the activities	
Sex	%	<i>Years worked</i>	
Female	51	Average (standard deviation)	5.52 (7.32)
Male	48	Number of people	
I prefer not to say	1	Average (standard deviation)	13.8 (21)
<i>Age</i>		<i>Activity sector</i>	%
Average (standard deviation)	33.8 (10.9)	Administrative	7
<i>Educational level</i>	%	Comercial	7
Secondary education	5	Accounting	7
Undergraduate degree	24	Education	33
Especialization degree	37	Finance	7
Master's degree	24	Others	38
PhD degree	10		

Source: research data.

Regarding activities, the average number of years worked is approximately 6 years (5.52) with a standard deviation of (7.32). The average number of people worked with directly is approximately 14 people (13.8) with a standard deviation of 21 people. The area of activity that stood out the most was education with 33% (n=27) of the sample, followed by the administrative, commercial, accounting and financial areas, each with 7% (n=6), and the option "other" represented the varied responses and had 38% (n=31) of the research participants.

In the hypothesis test, the results of the first hypothesis can be verified in Table 3. H1 was: In relation to groups without a connector, groups that include a connector will have lower turnover intentions.

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Table 3 – Personal and collective identification and professional perspective

Independent Variables	Estimative	t	p
Intercepto	3.10471	4.2	< .001
IP	-0.24833	-1.508	0.136
IC	0.33055	2.111	0.038
Years works	-0.01387	-0.577	0.565
Number of persons	0.0064	0.788	0.433
Activity sector	-0.17852	-1.831	0.071

Source: research data.

This hypothesis was partially supported, as it was found that having a connector in the work group (IP) + (IC) is related to professional outlook (PP). The independent variables (IP) and (IC) were not separated, as the objective was not to determine whether the connector was the respondent or a coworker. The results showed that most respondents were not the connectors themselves, but rather identified a coworker as the connector, since tests were conducted separately for IP and IC.

In the case of this hypothesis (H1), IP did not show significant or positive results ($\beta = -0.248$; $p = 0.136$), whereas IC showed positive and significant results ($\beta = 0.330$; $p = 0.038$), indicating that the presence of a connector increases the likelihood that an individual will remain in the organization. The removal of the IP variable from the model was tested; however, this affected the IC variable, leading to weaker significance (results not tabulated). For this reason, IP was retained in the H1 test model.

Organizations have the option to hire and assign connectors to work teams as a personnel control strategy. Employee selection and placement procedures aim to help organizations identify individuals with the appropriate skills and values for a role and position them in an environment where they are motivated, engaged, and able to perform their tasks efficiently, with the goal of maximizing revenues and reducing costs (MERCHANT & VAN DER STEDE, 2017).

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It is well established that high turnover can increase organizational costs due to additional expenses related to employee replacement, training, among others. Relationships within the work group and among its members exert a strong influence on employees' job satisfaction and their intention to remain in the organization (DESS & SHAW, 2001; EHRHARDT & RAGINS, 2019; MOWDAY et al., 1982; RIKETTA & VAN DICK, 2005). Following this line of reasoning, the second hypothesis tested whether there is a relationship between the level of satisfaction and turnover intention.

Thus, H2 aimed to identify whether groups with at least one connector and a high level of satisfaction would have lower turnover intentions than groups with at least one connector and a low level of satisfaction. The results can be observed in Table 4.

Table 4 – Personal and collective identification and job satisfaction

Independent variables	Estimative	t	p
Intercepto	4.62782	6.62	< .001
IP	-0.11174	-0.776	0.44
IC	0.64207	4.36	< .001
STF	-0.80088	-5.255	< .001
Years worked	-0.00349	-0.168	0.867
Number of people	0.00767	1.097	0.276
Activity sector	-0.21127	-2.511	0.014

Source: reserach data.

This hypothesis was supported, as it was found that having a connector in the work group (IP) + (IC) is positively related to job satisfaction (STF). Once again, IP presented a negative and non-significant result ($\beta = -0.111$; $p = 0.44$), whereas IC showed significant and positive results ($\beta = 0.642$; $p < 0.001$), indicating that identification with the collective increases the likelihood that an individual will remain in the organization. Satisfaction presented an estimate of ($\beta = -0.8$; $p < 0.001$), suggesting that the level of satisfaction with the company may result in a lower intention to remain in the organization. It is important to highlight that, in this hypothesis, the independent variables (IP) and (IC) were also not

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separated, as mentioned in H1, since the objective was not to determine whether the connector was the respondent or another employee. When testing this hypothesis, it was observed that IP does not significantly influence the model, while the other variables showed significant results.

Individuals who are perceived as - or feel - different from other group members generally report lower satisfaction with their group experience, lower integration in group activities and communication, as well as weaker attachment to the group or a greater motivation to leave it (GUILLAUME et al., 2012; JACKSON et al., 1991; RIORDAN & SHORE, 1997; ZATZICK, ELVIRA & COHEN, 2003). Thus, H3 aimed to identify whether groups with at least one connector and a high level of identification with the organization would have lower turnover intentions than groups with at least one connector and a low level of identification with the organization. The results can be observed in Table 5.

Table 5 – Personal and collective identification and identification

Independent variables	Estimative	t	P
Intercepto	3.83909	5.4431	< .001
IP	-0.14477	-0.9422	0.349
IC	0.52888	3.4618	< .001
IG	-0.54025	-3.8716	< .001
Years workd	-0.00184	-0.0823	0.935
Number of persons	0.00652	0.8732	0.385
Activity sector	-0.16562	-1.8472	0.069

Fonte: dados da pesquisa.

This hypothesis was supported, as it was found that having a connector in the work group (IP) + (IC) is positively related to group identification (IG) and, consequently, to professional outlook (PP). Once again, there was no separation between the independent variables (IP) and (IC), as in H1 and H2. The results indicate that IP ($\beta = -0.144$; $p = 0.349$) was neither significant nor positive, while IC showed a positive and significant estimate ($\beta = 0.528$; $p < 0.001$), demonstrating that collective identification contributes to employee retention. Group identification presented a result of ($\beta = -0.54$; $p < 0.001$), indicating that,

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depending on the level of identification with the group, it may lead to a lower intention to remain in the current organization.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to contribute by addressing two research gaps. The first was to determine whether the presence of at least one connector in an organization positively influences the reduction of employees' turnover intentions. The second was to verify whether connectors within organizational environments can be considered a tool for reducing turnover costs.

Accordingly, three hypotheses were developed and tested in order to identify whether there are employees who perceive themselves as connectors within the organizational environment, or whether they can identify other coworkers as connectors. It was also tested whether it was possible to identify the relationship between these connectors and employees' level of job satisfaction, professional outlook, and identification with their group.

After testing the proposed hypotheses, it was found that they were fully or partially supported. H1 was partially supported, as it was verified that having a connector in the work group (IP) + (IC) is related to professional outlook (PP). H2 was supported, as it was found that having a connector in the work group (IP) + (IC) is positively related to job satisfaction (STF). Finally, H3 was also supported, as it was verified that having a connector in the work group (IP) + (IC) is positively related to group identification (IG) and, consequently, to professional outlook (PP).

These findings suggest that connectors play an important role in organizational dynamics, positively influencing the work environment and contributing to employee well-being and success. They can act as facilitators of relationships, promote effective communication, and enhance collaboration within teams. Moreover, the presence of connectors within an organization may

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have a positive impact on reducing turnover costs, as it was found that companies with connectors have a lower likelihood of employee turnover.

The results may have significant implications for human resource management and for the development of strategies aimed at identifying, valuing, and promoting connectors within organizations. This may contribute to the creation of a more positive and productive work environment, in which employees feel more engaged, satisfied, and motivated.

Thus, this study contributes by testing hypotheses that relate the presence of connector individuals to professional outlook, job satisfaction, and group identification. This contribution represents a theoretical advancement that may help companies manage their human resources more efficiently and effectively, with the aim of strategically reducing costs.

The study's limitations provide opportunities for future research, such as identifying whether companies with connectors have lower turnover costs compared to those without connectors. Additionally, future studies may examine the personal characteristics and personality traits of connectors.

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REFERENCES

ALVES, I.; LOURENÇO, S. M. Subjective performance evaluation and managerial work outcomes. *Accounting and Business Research*. DOI: 10.1080/00014788.2021.1959292.

ASHFORTH, B. E.; MAEL, F. Teoria da identidade social e organização. *Academy of Management Review*, v. 14, n. 1, p. 20–39, 1989.

AUTREY, R. L.; BAUER, J.; JACKSON, D.; KLEVSKY, J. Deploying “connectors”: A control to manage employee turnover intentions? *Accounting, Organizations and Society*. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aos.2019.101059>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

BECKER, J. L. Estatística básica. Grupo A, 2015. Disponível em: <https://app.minhabiblioteca.com.br/books/9788582603130>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

COSTIGAN, R. D.; INSINGA, R. C.; BERMAN, J. J.; KRANAS, G.; KURESHOV, V. A. Revisitando a relação da confiança do supervisor e da confiança do CEO com as intenções de rotatividade: um estudo comparativo de três países. *Journal of World Business*, v. 46, n. 1, p. 74–83, 2011.

DESS, G. G.; SHAW, J. D. Voluntary turnover, social capital, and organizational performance. *Academy of Management Review*, v. 26, n. 3, p. 446–456, 2001.

ELLEMERS, N.; KORTEKAAS, P.; OUWERKERK, J. W. Autocategorização, compromisso com o grupo e auto-estima do grupo como aspectos relacionados mas distintos da identidade social. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, v. 29, n. 2-3, p. 371–389, 1999.

FAIA, V. S. O efeito moderador do sistema de controle de vendas na adoção da ambidestria serviços-vendas. Dissertação (Mestrado) – Universidade Estadual de Maringá, Centro de Ciências Sociais Aplicadas, Programa de Pós-graduação em Administração, Maringá, PR, Brasil, 2014.

FISHER, J. G.; MAINES, L. A.; PEFFER, S. A.; SPRINKLE, G. B. Uma investigação experimental da discricionariedade do empregador na avaliação de desempenho e remuneração dos funcionários. *The Accounting Review*, v. 80, n. 2, p. 563–583, 2005.

RELISE

70

GALLUCCI, M.; JENTSCHKE, S. SEMLj: jamovi SEM Analysis. [jamovi module]. Disponível em: <https://semlj.github.io/>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

GELENCSÉR, M.; SZABÓ-SZENTGRÓTI, G.; KÖEMŰVES, Z. S.; HOLLÓSY-VADÁSZ, G. The Holistic Model of Labour Retention: The Impact of Workplace Wellbeing Factors on Employee Retention. *Administrative Sciences*, v. 13, artigo 5, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci13050121>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

GIBBS, M.; MERCHANT, K.; VAN DER STEDE, W.; VARGUS, M. Determinantes e efeitos da subjetividade em incentivos. *The Accounting Review*, v. 79, n. 2, p. 409–446, 2004.

HAESEBROUCK, K.; VAN DEN ABBEELE, A.; WILLIAMSON, M. G. Building trust through knowledge sharing: Implications for incentive system design. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aos.2021.101241>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

JENSEN, M. C.; MECKLING, W. H. Specific and General Knowledge and Organizational Structure. *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, v. 8, n. 2, p. 251–274, 1995. Disponível em: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=6658>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

JONES, T. M. Teoria instrumental dos stakeholders: uma síntese de ética e economia. *Academy of Management Review*, v. 20, n. 2, p. 404–437, 1995.

KELTNER, D.; KOGAN, A.; PIFF, P. K.; SATURN, S. R. The sociocultural appraisals, values, and emotions (SAVE) framework of prosociality: Core processes from gene to meme. *Annual Review of Psychology*, v. 65, p. 425–446, 2014.

LAU, C. M.; BUCKLAND, C. Orçamento – o papel da confiança e da participação: uma nota de pesquisa. *Abacus*, v. 37, n. 3, p. 369–388, 2001.

LAU, C. M.; WONG, K. M.; EGGLETON, I. R. C. Equidade dos procedimentos de avaliação de desempenho e satisfação no trabalho: o papel dos efeitos baseados e não baseados em resultados. *Accounting and Business Research*, v. 38, n. 2, p. 121–136, 2008.

LUZ, D. O. da; BOENTE, A. N. P. Estudo dos fatores influenciadores de rotatividade de funcionários: teoria dos conjuntos Fuzzy. *Revista de Gestão e*

RELISE

71

Secretariado, v. 15, n. 8, p. e4053, 2024. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.7769/gesec.v15i8.4053>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

MAYER, R. C.; DAVIS, J. H. O efeito do sistema de avaliação de desempenho na confiança dos gestores: um quase-experimento de campo. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, v. 84, n. 1, p. 123–136, 1999.

MATIAS-PEREIRA, J. *Manual de Metodologia da Pesquisa Científica*. 4. ed. Grupo GEN, 2016.

MCEVOY, G. M.; CASCIO, W. F. Do good or bad performers leave? A meta-analysis of the relationship between performance and turnover. *Academy of Management Journal*, v. 30, n. 4, p. 744–762, 1987.

MILGROM, P.; ROBERTS, J. *Economics, Organization & Management*. Prentice Hall, 1992.

MINTZBERG, H.; et al. *The strategy process*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1988.

PARKER, S. K. Beyond motivation: Job and work design for development, health, ambidexterity, and more. *Annual Review of Psychology*, v. 65, p. 661–680, 2014.

PENNER, L. A.; DOVIDIO, J. F.; PILIAVIN, J. A.; SCHROEDER, D. A. Prosocial behavior: Multilevel perspectives. *Annual Review of Psychology*, v. 56, p. 365–390, 2005.

PENTLAND, A. To signal is human. *American Scientist*, v. 98, n. 3, p. 204–210, 2010.

PRENDERGAST, C.; TOPEL, R. Discriminação e viés na avaliação de desempenho. *European Economic Review*, v. 37, n. 2-3, p. 355–365, 1993.

R CORE TEAM. R: A Language and environment for statistical computing. Version 4.1. Disponível em: <https://cran.r-project.org>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

RADTKE, R. R.; SPEKLE, R. F.; WIDENER, S. K. Flourish or flounder: Do trust-centric management controls encourage knowledge sharing and team performance? *Accounting, Organizations and Society*. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aos.2022.101429>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

RELISE

REVELLE, W. psych: Procedures for Psychological, Psychometric, and Personality Research. Disponível em: <https://cran.r-project.org/package=psych>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

ROCHA, W. Gestão estratégica. Faculdade de Economia, Administração e Contabilidade da Universidade de São Paulo, 1999.

SANTOS, M. I. da C.; SANTOS, R. F. dos. Análise da rotatividade de pessoal como um tipo de custo oculto em uma empresa do setor de vidros. *Revista Ambiente Contábil*, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, v. 14, n. 2, p. 338–356, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.21680/2176-9036.2022v14n2ID24088>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

SHAW, J. D.; GUPTA, N.; DELERY, J. E. Alternative conceptualizations of the relationship between voluntary turnover and organizational performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, v. 48, n. 1, p. 50–68, 2005.

SHERIDAN, J. E. Organizational culture and employee retention. *Academy of Management Journal*, v. 35, n. 5, p. 1036–1056, 1992.

SHOLIHIN, M.; PIKE, R. Equidade na avaliação de desempenho e suas consequências comportamentais. *Accounting and Business Research*, v. 39, n. 4, p. 397–413, 2009.

THE JAMOVI PROJECT. jamovi. Version 2.3. Disponível em: <https://www.jamovi.org>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

VAN DICK, R.; GROJEAN, M. W.; CHRIST, O.; WIESEKE, J. Identidade e a milha extra: relações entre identificação organizacional e comportamento de cidadania organizacional. *British Journal of Management*, v. 17, n. 4, p. 283–301, 2006.

VAN RINSUM, M.; VERBEETEN, F. H. M. O impacto da subjetividade nas práticas de avaliação de desempenho na motivação dos gestores do setor público. *Accounting and Business Research*, v. 42, n. 4, p. 377–396, 2012.

WALLIMAN, N. Métodos de Pesquisa. Saraiva, 2015. Disponível em: <https://app.minhabiblioteca.com.br/books/9788502629857>. Acesso em: 17 jan. 2025.

RELISE

73

WALUMBWA, F. O.; AVOLIO, B. J.; ZHU, W. Como a liderança transformacional tece sua influência no desempenho individual do trabalho: o papel das crenças de identificação e eficácia. *Psicologia Pessoal*, v. 61, n. 4, p. 793–825, 2008.

APPENDIX 1 – QUESTIONNAIRE APPLIED

	Olá! Este questionário faz parte de uma pesquisa realizada pelas mestrandas Eloisa Aparecida Cecília dos Santos e Rafaela Amâncio Armacollo e orientadas pelo prof. Valter Faia do Departamento de Ciências Contábeis da Universidade Estadual de Maringá.						
Este estudo busca verificar a interação entre grupos dentro de uma organização e os controles gerenciais. A participação nesta pesquisa é voluntária . Você pode optar por não participar ou desistir de continuar a qualquer momento. As respostas são confidenciais e apenas para uso acadêmico . Nenhuma resposta será analisada individualmente, mas sim os resultados consolidados. A participação na pesquisa é rápida e levará no máximo 15 minutos. Caso surjam dúvidas, entre em contato por e-mail: pg404398@uem.br / pg404402@uem.br . Muito obrigada pela sua colaboração, ela é muito importante para esta pesquisa							
ATIVIDADES DE INTERATIVIDADE: As frases abaixo dizem respeito às atividades e interatividade entre os funcionários dentro de uma organização. Como funcionário de sua empresa, avalie se você discorda ou concorda com as frases abaixo. Depois marque um "X" no grau de sua concordância ou discordância. A escala varia de discordo totalmente (1), discordo parcialmente (2), nem concordo e nem discordo (3), concordo parcialmente (4) e concordo totalmente (5). Não há resposta certa ou errada, o que se busca é a sua opinião.							
Avalie as afirmações abaixo a respeito de SUA INTERATIVIDADE dentro da empresa.			Discordo Totalmente		\Leftrightarrow	Concordo Totalmente	
			1	2	3	4	5
1	Eu gasto muito tempo e esforço auxiliando outras pessoas.						
2	Sou capaz de fazer com que a maioria das pessoas se sinta confortável e à vontade perto de mim.						
3	Sempre pareço saber instintivamente as coisas certas a dizer ou fazer para influenciar os outros.						
4	Muitas vezes sou o elo entre indivíduos em diferentes grupos dentro de minha empresa.						
5	Muitas vezes me pego apresentando as pessoas umas às outras em meu ambiente de trabalho.						
6	Tento reunir pessoas de meu trabalho que conheço quando acho que elas se considerariam interessantes.						
7	Frequentemente descubro que sou a conexão entre pessoas que de outra forma não se conheceriam dentro de uma organização						
8	As pessoas que conheço em meu ambiente de trabalho geralmente se conhecem por minha causa.						
Avalie as afirmações abaixo a respeito da INTERATIVIDADE DE SEUS COLEGAS dentro da empresa.			Discordo Totalmente		\Leftrightarrow	Concordo Totalmente	
			1	2	3	4	5
1	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo e gastam muito tempo e esforço auxiliando outras pessoas.						
2	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo que são capazes de fazer com que a maioria das pessoas se sinta confortável e à vontade perto de dela(s).						
3	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo que parecem saber instintivamente as coisas certas a dizer ou fazer para influenciar os outros.						

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4	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo que são o elo entre indivíduos em diferentes grupos dentro de minha empresa.					
5	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo que apresentam as pessoas umas às outras em meu ambiente de trabalho.					
6	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo que tentam reunir pessoas de meu trabalho quando acham que elas se considerariam interessantes.					
7	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo que frequentemente são a conexão entre pessoas que de outra forma não se conheceriam dentro da organização.					
8	Existe uma ou mais pessoas que trabalham comigo que, em meu ambiente de trabalho, geralmente se conhecem por causa dela(s).					
Avalie as afirmações abaixo sobre o seu GRAU DE SATISFAÇÃO dentro da empresa.		Discordo Totalmente		↔	Concordo Totalmente	
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Tenho muito orgulho de poder dizer às pessoas que sou membro desta equipe de trabalho.					
2	Sinto-me parte da organização.					
3	Eu não recomendaria um amigo próximo para se juntar à nossa equipe.					
4	Meus colegas de trabalho me auxiliam quanto às orientações a respeito de como devem conduzir suas ações para o alcance dos objetivos e metas.					
5	É importante que eu perceba que as pessoas do meu trabalho são sinceras e me auxiliem em minhas atividades quando necessário.					
6	Eu não me sinto à vontade em solicitar auxílio de meus colegas de trabalho para desenvolver minhas atividades.					
7	Eu sinto que não posso confiar nos meus colegas de trabalho.					
8	Eu sinto que a maioria das pessoas do meu ambiente de trabalho não compartilham os seus conhecimentos e informações.					
Avalie as afirmações abaixo a respeito de sua PERSPECTIVA PROFISSIONAL dentro da empresa.		Discordo Totalmente		↔	Concordo Totalmente	
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Muitas vezes penso em sair da empresa.					
2	Provavelmente procurarei um novo emprego no próximo ano.					
3	Pretendo continuar nesta empresa por muito tempo.					
Avalie as afirmações abaixo a respeito de sua IDENTIFICAÇÃO em relação à empresa.		Discordo Totalmente		↔	Concordo Totalmente	
		1	2	3	4	5

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1	Consigo identificar oportunidades de crescimento dentro desta empresa.				
2	Me sinto acolhido e motivado quando recebo auxílio de meus colegas de trabalho, fazendo com que queira continuar na empresa.				
3	Quando não posso contar com o auxílio de meus colegas de trabalho, penso em sair da empresa.				
4	Mesmo que eu goste de desempenhar minhas funções, penso em sair da empresa pela falta de cooperação entre os colegas de trabalho.				
5	A baixa interatividade entre meus colegas de trabalho faz com que eu pense em sair da empresa.				

CARACTERIZAÇÃO: A pesquisa agora está no fim. As perguntas agora são apenas para traçar um perfil dos participantes da pesquisa.

Há quantos anos você trabalha em sua atual empresa? (anos completos)		Com quantas pessoas você trabalha diretamente?	
Qual setor/área de atuação?			
Qual o seu sexo?	() Feminino Masculino () Prefiro não dizer	Qual a sua idade?	
Qual seu grau de escolaridade completo?	() Ensino Fundamental () Ensino Médio	() Ensino Superior () Especialização	() Outro, qual?
Se desejar receber o resultado desta pesquisa, informe seu e-mail para que seja possível o envio dos resultados.			